

Title	First version of virtual access to the tools for analysing and plotting atmospheric long time series across RIs at the website atmo-access.eu
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ATMO ACCESS
Access to Atmospheric Research Facilities

1. Introduction

This Milestone concerns a virtual access to the cross-RI timeseries analysis service.

The service was described in the Deliverable 5.5, available at:

https://www7.obs-mip.fr/wp-content-aeris/uploads/sites/82/2023/05/ATMO-ACCESS_D5.5.pdf

2. Service

The service is available at the address:

<https://permalink.aeris-data.fr/atmo-access-timeseries>

and is accessible through Atmo-Access Virtual Access portal:

<https://www.atmo-access.eu/virtual-access>

